

Numerical investigation of the impact of solids flow control on the performance of the calcium looping process

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ABSTRACT

Calcium looping (CaL) is a promising post-combustion carbon capture technology that employs a dual fluidized bed reactor system to cyclically capture and release CO₂. The efficiency of the CaL process strongly depends on controlling key operating conditions, such as reactor temperatures and the transfer of solids between reactors. This study presents a numerical investigation of solids flow control and its impact on CaL performance using a 1.5D modeling approach. The model, developed in the Simulink environment, is validated against experimental data from the 1.7 MW_{th} La Pereda pilot plant. The study analyzes how controlling the transfer rate of solids between reactors affects reactor temperatures and CO₂ capture efficiency. The results show that precise control of solids transfer significantly expands the operating window of the system and may enable more efficient CO₂ capture. By recycling part of the solids back to the carbonator and adjusting the fuel feeding rate, the capture efficiency of the simulated scenario could be increased by up to 9 percentage points, reaching a 90 % efficiency. These findings highlight the importance of developing reliable and scalable solids control strategies to ensure efficient operation of the CaL process.

1. Introduction

Calcium looping (CaL) was first proposed by Shimizu et al. (1999) as a post-combustion process to remove carbon dioxide (CO₂) from flue gases of coal power plants. It comprises two fluidized bed reactors, the calciner and carbonator, between which a calcium-based sorbent is cycled. The core working principle of the process is the reversible calcination–carbonation reaction

Calcium oxide (CaO) and CO₂ present in the flue gases react in the carbonator, forming calcium carbonate (CaCO₃). As the forward reaction is exothermic, cooling is needed to maintain the reactor at its design temperature, and the heat extracted is used to generate power. The CO₂-lean gas is separated from the solids in a solids separator and released into the atmosphere. The CaCO₃ produced is regenerated back to CaO and CO₂ (Eq. (1), backward reaction) in the calciner, after which the solids and gases are separated in a second solids separator. Typically, heat for calcination is supplied by the combustion of a fuel in the calciner. The fuel is preferably fired under oxy-combustion conditions in order to achieve a high CO₂ concentration at the gas outlet (Hanak et al., 2018). The CaO is transported back to the carbonator to continue the

looping cycle, while the CO₂-rich gases are led to a gas processing unit for conditioning. The activity of the sorbent is maintained by a constant feed of make-up, while ash and spent sorbent are removed in the form of purge.

The performance of the CaL process is largely determined by the carbon capture efficiency of the carbonator:

$$E_{carb} = 1 - \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{out}}}{\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{in}}} \quad (2)$$

Calcium looping has been found to be an effective method for CO₂ removal, with capture efficiencies of 90 % commonly demonstrated in pilot operations with circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactors (Arias et al., 2013; Ströhle et al., 2014), and capture efficiencies as high as 99 % achieved under special conditions (Arias et al., 2024). The maximum capture efficiency is limited by equilibrium, with temperatures below 650 °C required to reduce the partial pressure of CO₂ below 1.2 kPa (Stanmore and Gilot, 2005). For this reason, the carbonator is typically operated at temperatures between 600 and 700 °C. In addition to a suitable temperature, sufficiently high sorbent inventory and activity are required for efficient carbon capture (Alonso et al., 2009; Romano, 2012; Diego and Arias, 2020; Arias et al., 2024). The average activity of the sorbent in the carbonator depends on a number of process parameters,

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Nomenclature

Greek symbols

ρ density [kg/m³]

Roman symbols

\dot{m}	mass flow [kg/s]
\dot{n}	molar flow [mol/s]
b	fraction of solids recycled [kg/kg]
C	concentration [mol/m ³]
E	energy [J], efficiency [–]
G_s	solids flux [kg/(m ² s)]
k	deactivation constant [–]
M	molar weight [kg/mol]
m	mass [kg]
n	amount [mol]
Q	heat [W]
R	universal gas constant [J/(mol K)]
r	reaction rate [kg/s], age fraction [mol/mol]
T	temperature [°C]
t	time [s]
u	gas velocity [m/s]
u_t	terminal velocity [m/s]
V	volume [m ³]
X	molar fraction [mol/mol _{Ca}]
X^*	relative conversion X/X_{\max} [mol/mol]
X_r	residual activity [mol/mol _{Ca}]
X_{\max}	CO ₂ -carrying capacity [mol/mol _{Ca}]
z	elevation (from grid) [m]

such as the flow of CaO transferred from the calciner to the carbonator and its carbonate content, the make-up flow fed into the system, the amount of CO₂ being captured, and the temperature at which carbonation occurs (Rodríguez et al., 2010; Charitos et al., 2011; Criado et al., 2018).

In order to ensure a sufficient supply of active CaO to the carbonator, the calciner must be operated efficiently, ideally with near complete conversion of CaCO₃ to CaO (Arias et al., 2013; Ströhle et al., 2020). Since CaCO₃ is calcined in a stream of concentrated CO₂ and high reaction rates are desired, the calciner is typically operated at relatively high temperatures, in the range of 850–950 °C (Arias et al., 2013; Ströhle et al., 2020). Increasing the temperature above 950 °C is generally considered unfeasible due to higher fuel consumption and sorbent sintering, which leads to its early deactivation (Grasa et al., 2009; Hanak et al., 2018). The heat demand of the calciner mainly depends on the carbon capture efficiency, the temperature difference between reactors, the make-up flow, and the flows of gas and solids entering the reactors (Ströhle et al., 2020).

The transfer of solids between reactors is an essential part of the CaL process. The entrainment rate of solids is determined by the hydrodynamic conditions in the reactors and grows steeply as the superficial velocity is increased (Charitos et al., 2010a; Diego et al., 2012; Diego and Arias, 2020). In addition to supplying the carbonator with calcined sorbent, these solids transport large amounts of sensible heat, which heavily impacts the temperatures of both reactors. Charitos et al. (2010a) estimated that operating the carbonator with superficial velocities larger than 4 m/s could lead to temperature control problems unless the flow of solids was restricted. Similar results were obtained by Ylätaalo et al. (2013), who found that achieving a sufficient temperature difference between the two reactors was challenging if the flow of solids transferred between the reactors was too high. Excessive entrainment in the carbonator may also make it challenging to maintain a sufficiently dense bed for efficient carbon capture (Diego et al., 2012; Arias et al., 2013; Diego and Arias, 2020). For these reasons, several existing CaL pilot plants (Ströhle et al., 2020; Diego and Arias, 2020; Horn-

berger et al., 2021) are equipped with flow control systems. Mechanical systems include valves such as plug valves and double flap valves, as described in patents (Schaker et al., 1997; Chrysostome and Borgnat, 1985), as well as screw conveyors used mainly in pilot-scale installations (Dziva et al., 2025; Magli, 2023). However, mechanical devices are prone to wear, fouling, and operational disruptions such as blockage or jamming. Non-mechanical, fluidization-based approaches rely on aerated loop seal configurations to regulate solids transfer without moving parts. Common designs include U-shaped loop seals, L-valves, and other fluidized arrangements that maintain or interrupt solid flow by adjusting aeration (Rosnell and Kettunen, 2020; Liang et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2017). These systems are advantageous in high-temperature and abrasive environments due to their simplicity and reduced maintenance requirements.

These control systems allow the decoupling of the flow of solids transferred between reactors from their entrainment rate by recycling part of the entrained solids back to the same reactor, as illustrated in Fig. 1. While the flows of solids led to the same reactor (streams 7 and 8) and the other reactor (streams 9 and 10) are sometimes referred to as internal and external circulation, respectively, these same terms are commonly used in the CFB literature with a different meaning (Horio et al., 1988; Yang et al., 2022). To prevent misunderstandings, streams (7) and (8) will be referred to as the recycle streams, and streams (9) and (10) as the transfer streams throughout this work. Although recycling solids may facilitate temperature control, the reduced flow of CaO to the carbonator, combined with the dependency of the CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent on the carbonation temperature (Criado et al., 2018), is expected to weaken sorbent activity. As such, recycling part of the solids affects the overall performance of the process through several interrelated mechanisms, which, to the best of the authors' knowledge, have not been previously explored in detail.

In this work, the effect of solids flow control systems on process performance is demonstrated. The objective of this work is to highlight the importance of controlling solids flows to reach suitable temperatures in both reactors for efficient operation of the calcium looping system. A 1.5D modeling tool for dual CFB reactors is used, and the model is validated with experimental results. The model couples the two reactors through material and heat capacity flows and contains the most important physical descriptions of the flow, reactions, and heat transfer within the reactors. Reactor temperatures are adjusted by varying the fuel input and the share of recycled solids. The main contribution of this work lies in the modeling results, which demonstrate that carbon capture efficiency is highly sensitive to the magnitude of solids transfer between reactors and that increasing solids transfer past a certain point may impair the overall performance of the process. These results emphasize the importance of accurately and flexibly controlling solid flows and highlight the need for reliable double-exit loop-seal solutions to enable effective process operation in practical applications.

2. Methodology

The simulations for this study were conducted using a CaL model built in the Simulink environment (Ylätaalo et al., 2012). The model consists of two CFB reactors, which are connected such that the solids exiting either reactor can be redirected back to the two reactors in an arbitrary distribution. This setup allows simulating the operation of the CaL process with different splits between solids recycle and transfer flows in either reactor, as illustrated in Fig. 1. These splits are defined by two parameters, b_{CB} and b_{CC} , which are the mass flow ratios of the recycled flow to the total flow, i.e., the ratio of stream (7) to stream (3) for the carbonator (b_{CB}) and stream (8) to stream (4) for the calciner (b_{CC}), as shown below.

$$b_{CB} = \frac{\dot{m}_{s,7}}{\dot{m}_{s,3}} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 1. Illustration of calcium looping process model with controllable transfer streams.

$$b_{CC} = \frac{\dot{m}_{s,8}}{\dot{m}_{s,4}} \quad (4)$$

This study focuses on the effects of such a split on the performance of the CaL process, and we make no assumptions about how the split itself is achieved in practice.

2.1. 1.5D reactor model

1D and 1.5D models (Ylätaalo et al., 2012; Romano, 2012; Ströhle et al., 2014) are commonly used when modeling the CaL process, as they offer relatively accurate results (Martínez et al., 2016) of the process with low computational costs. Generally speaking, the main limitations of 1D and 1.5D models are the inherent assumption that elements are well mixed and their reliance on simplified models for reactor hydrodynamics. The gas and solid phases are assumed to share the same temperature in each element. The well-mixed assumption holds reasonably well for reactors with a small cross-sectional area, such as those simulated here, but becomes questionable when applied to the simulation of large-scale reactors. The axial density profile is validated through pressure measurements in the reactor, and the range of fluidizing gas velocities used in this work is typical for CFBs.

In this work, two 1.5D CFB reactor modules are used to model the two reactors. The reactor modules support any number of gas and solid input streams into any position in the reactor. A purge stream can be defined to remove material from the bottom-most element of the reactor. Gases and solids exit the reactor through an exit opening that may span multiple elements, but in this study, they simply exit through the top-most element. The model itself comprises four main parts that are solved

in order, namely kinetic reactions, gaseous mass balances, solid mass balances, and energy balances.

Each reactor is discretized longitudinally into 40 elements and radially into a core and an annulus region, resulting in a total of 80 elements per reactor. Transient mass and energy balances are written for each of the 80 elements. The mass balance of species j in element i may be expressed in general form as:

$$\frac{dm_{j,i}}{dt} = \sum_{in} \dot{m}_{j,i} - \sum_{out} \dot{m}_{j,i} + \sum_{reaction} r_{j,i}, \quad (5)$$

where m are masses, \dot{m} are mass flows, and r are the mass source terms linked to reactions. Gases are assumed to flow following a plug flow, whereas the flow of solids depends on the distribution of solids and will be presented later. Similarly, the energy balance of element i is given by:

$$\frac{dE_i}{dt} = \sum_{solid} Q_{adv,i} + \sum_{gas} Q_{adv,i} + \sum_{solid} Q_{disp,i} + \sum Q_{HT,i} + \sum_{reaction} Q_{r,i}, \quad (6)$$

where Q_{adv} is the sensible heat carried into or out of the element by advection, Q_{disp} is the heat transfer between neighboring elements by solids dispersion, Q_{HT} refers to heat transfer to cooling surfaces or heat losses, and Q_r are source terms associated with reactions. Heat transfer coefficients for heat transfer surfaces are obtained from the correlation of Dutta and Basu (2002). The coefficients are reduced by 25 % for internal heat exchangers following Basu's recommendation for wing walls (Basu, 2006). Time-dependent equations for the energy and mass balance are solved with a first-order difference method utilizing the forward Euler method. Convective flows are differentiated with the upwind method, and diffusion of energy is differentiated with the central

difference method. Results for the reactors are obtained by solving the mass and energy balances using ordinary differential equation (ODE) solvers available in Simulink. Steady-state solutions are obtained by running the simulations to convergence while keeping the boundary conditions constant.

Fluidization is a complex phenomenon, and a great deal of effort has been invested in attempting to model it accurately (Ghadirian et al., 2019; Stamatopoulos et al., 2023). Such methods are, however, prohibitively expensive to use in process simulation tools, where an approximate solids distribution is sufficient to evaluate process performance. For this reason, the axial distribution of solids in the reactor is given by the simpler semi-empirical correlation of Johnsson and Leckner (Johnsson and Leckner, 1995):

$$\rho_s(z) = (\rho_{s,0} - \rho_{s,e} \exp(KZ_e)) \exp(-az) + \rho_{s,e} \exp(K(Z_e - z)), \quad (7)$$

where $\rho_{s,0}$ and $\rho_{s,e}$ are the solids densities at the bottom and exit of the reactor, respectively; Z_e is the elevation at the center of the exit opening, and a and K are decay coefficients for the splash and dilute zones, and are given by Johnsson and Leckner (1995):

$$a = 4u_t/u, \quad (8)$$

$$K = 0.23/(u - u_t), \quad (9)$$

where u is the gas velocity and u_t is the terminal velocity of the particles. The mass density of solids at the exit of the reactor and the mass flux of solids carried to the cyclone are given by two correlations proposed by Ylätaalo et al. (2012):

$$\rho_{s,e} = c_{exit} \rho_{avg} \frac{u - u_t}{u_{pn} - u_t}, \quad (10)$$

$$G_s = c_{circ} u \rho_{s,e}^{0.8}. \quad (11)$$

Here, ρ_{avg} is the total solids density in the reactor, u_{pn} is the pneumatic transport velocity of the particles ($20u_t$ for small particles Kunii and Levenspiel, 1991), and c_{exit} and c_{circ} are empirical parameters (Secomandi et al., 2024).

The internal circulation of solids in CFBs arises from a layer of solids flowing down along the walls, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The mass flow of solids passing from the core region to the wall layer at element i is given by:

$$\dot{m}_{toWL,i} = u_{toWL} \rho_{s,i} A_{w,i}. \quad (12)$$

where $A_{w,i}$ is the wall area of element i and u_{toWL} is the average velocity with which solids enter the wall layer. The primary effect of the wall layer flow is reducing temperature differences between the top and bottom regions of the reactor, and as such, the most reliable way to determine u_{toWL} is through energy balances of the lowest elements. Reactions and the physical space occupied by the wall layer are not considered.

The model supports six solid species (CaO, CaCO₃, CaSO₄, Ca(OH)₂, char, and SiO₂ representing ash and inerts) and thirteen gaseous species (O₂, N₂, CO₂, H₂O, NH₃, H₂S, CO, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₇H₈, H₂, NO, and SO₂). Fuel decomposes into moisture, volatiles, char, and ash according to its proximate analysis. Moisture and volatiles are released in the bottom region of the reactor following a freely chosen profile. A detailed account of the formation of different volatile species can be found in Ritvanen et al. (2021). In addition, kinetic expressions for fifteen combustion, gasification, and gas-solid reactions have been implemented. The rate at which CaO is consumed by carbonation (kg_{CaO}/s) in element i has been adapted from Grasa et al. (2009) and is given by

$$r_{carb,i} = 0.3429 \exp\left(\frac{-2309}{T_i}\right) (C_{CO_2,i} - C_{eq,i}) (X_{max} - X_{CaCO_3,i})^{2/3} \times X_{CaO,i}^{0.1} n_{Ca,i} M_{CaO}, \quad (13)$$

where X_{max} , X_{CaCO_3} , and X_{CaO} are the maximum carbonate content and the contents of CaCO₃ and CaO in the sorbent, given as fractions of all calcium-containing compounds, e.g., n_{CaCO_3}/n_{Ca} . $n_{Ca,i}$ is the total amount of calcium in element i , while C_{CO_2} and C_{eq} are the actual and equilibrium CO₂ concentrations, the latter being given by Stanmore and Gilot (2005):

$$C_{eq} = \frac{4.137 \times 10^{12}}{RT} \exp\left(-\frac{20474}{T}\right). \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the rate at which CaCO₃ is consumed by calcination is obtained by combining expressions by Fang et al. (2009) and Martínez et al. (2012):

$$r_{calc,i} = c_{calc} 2057 \exp\left(\frac{-13470}{T_i}\right) (C_{eq,i} - C_{CO_2,i}) X_{CaCO_3,i}^{2/3} n_{Ca,i} M_{CaCO_3}. \quad (15)$$

where c_{calc} is a reaction calibration parameter. The temperatures in Eqs. (13)–(15) are given in Kelvin. Expressions for the remaining reactions can be found in Secomandi et al. (2024).

Fig. 2. Illustration of the internal circulation of solids induced by the wall layer.

2.2. Population balance model

A population balance model was built to estimate how operating condition changes affect the steady-state CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent, X_{\max} . It is calculated as the average of all age fractions in the system:

$$X_{\max} = \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} r_N X_{\max,N}, \quad (16)$$

where N is the number of calcination-carbonation cycles experienced by the particle (the “age” of the particle), r_N is the fraction of particles of age N , and $X_{\max,N}$ is the CO₂-carrying capacity of particles of age N . $X_{\max,N}$ has been fitted by Grasa and Abanades (2006) into an expression of the form:

$$X_{\max,N} = \frac{1}{1/(1 - X_r) + kN} + X_r, \quad (17)$$

where k is a deactivation constant and X_r is the residual activity after a large number of cycles. Criado et al. (2018) have correlated these two constants to the carbonation temperature (in degrees Kelvin):

$$k(T) = 0.0255 \exp\left(\frac{29300}{RT}\right), \quad (18)$$

$$X_r(T) = 1.04 \exp\left(\frac{-29300}{RT}\right). \quad (19)$$

Because the carbonator is not represented by a single temperature but by a range of local temperatures, the value used in these equations in this work is the carbonation-weighted average temperature over all 1D elements:

$$\bar{T}_{carb} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{elems}} r_{carb,i} T_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{elems}} r_{carb,i}}. \quad (20)$$

The age fractions are solved as state variables. Their balances are derived from a mass balance over the calciner, as described in Appendix A, and are given by the general expression:

$$\frac{dr_N}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{in}(r_{N-1} - r_N)(X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^*) + \dot{n}_0(r_{N,0} - r_N)}{n}, \quad (21)$$

where \dot{n}_{in} is the molar flow of calcium transferred from the carbonator into the calciner, \dot{n}_0 is the molar flow of CaCO₃ in the make-up, $r_{N,0}$ is the fraction of particles of age N in the make-up (equal to one for $N = 0$ and zero for all other age fractions), and n is the total calcium inventory in the system, in moles. X_{CC}^* and X_{CB}^* are the relative conversions (X/X_{\max}) of the calcined and carbonated sorbent, respectively, and this difference is related to the calcination rate as given by:

$$X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^* = \frac{\dot{n}_{calc} - (\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{in}r_0)E_{calc}}{\dot{n}_{in}X_{\max}}. \quad (22)$$

\dot{n}_{calc} is the total calcination occurring in the system at steady state (in mol/s) and is given by:

$$\dot{n}_{calc} = \dot{n}_{in}(X_{CB} - X_{CC}) + \dot{n}_0(1 - X_{CC}), \quad (23)$$

and E_{calc} is the calcination efficiency:

$$E_{calc} = \frac{\dot{n}_{calc}}{\dot{n}_{in}X_{CB} + \dot{n}_0}. \quad (24)$$

The dependence of $X_{\max,N}$ on the carbonation temperature poses a problem for time-dependent simulations since Eqs. (18) and (19) were obtained at constant carbonation temperatures (Criado et al., 2018). However, since the results presented in the current work are at steady state,

the dynamic response of X_{\max} to temperature need not be considered. X_{\max} is calculated using a truncated version of Eq. (16):

$$X_{\max} \approx \left[\sum_{N=1}^{N_{cut}-1} r_N X_{\max,N} + \left(1 - \sum_{N=0}^{N_{cut}-1} r_N\right) \frac{X_{\max,N_{cut}} + X_r}{2} \right] c_{X_{\max}}, \quad (25)$$

where $c_{X_{\max}}$ is an empirically determined sorbent CO₂-carrying coefficient to account for the deactivation of the sorbent due to sulphation and other non-idealities, and N_{cut} is the index of the last age fraction solved. The truncation error can be shown to be:

$$|\epsilon| \leq \left(1 - \sum_{N=0}^{N_{cut}-1} r_N\right) \frac{X_{\max,N_{cut}} - X_r}{2}. \quad (26)$$

Assuming a carbonation temperature of 650 °C and selecting $N_{cut} = 40$ results in a maximum truncation error of approximately 0.01 when the population is “infinitely old,” i.e., $\sum_{N=0}^{N_{cut}-1} r_N \approx 0$. However, this error is typically an order of magnitude smaller because most of the sorbent is distributed among the first forty age fractions.

2.3. La Pereda model

A model of the 1.7 MW_{th} La Pereda pilot plant was built and validated by steady-state measurements (Arias et al., 2018). The calciner and carbonator have inner diameters of 0.75 and 0.65 m, respectively, and are both 15 m high and refractory-lined. The carbonator is cooled by four bayonet tubes hanging inside the reactor, from the roof to an elevation of 3 m above the grid. The reactors are connected by two loop seals, which enable control of the recycle and transfer flows of solids by adjusting the position of a mechanical valve. The gas composition at the carbonator inlet and the outlet of both reactors is monitored by gas analyzers, whereas the solids composition is estimated through periodically taken samples. More detailed descriptions of the pilot plant are given by Sánchez-Biezma et al. (2011), Arias et al. (2013, 2018). The boundary conditions, model parameters, and fuel specifications are presented in Tables 1–3.

After validating the reference operating point, 87 other operating points were simulated, in which reactor temperatures were changed by systematically varying the fuel input and the solids recycling coefficient of the carbonator (b_{CB}). The fluidizing gas flow into the calciner was automatically adjusted to the changing fuel input by targeting a constant oxygen concentration of 10 v-%,db at the reactor outlet. While this is a relatively high value, it corresponds to the amount of oxygen fed into the calciner during the experiment (Arias et al., 2018). In order to focus on the effect of the two studied variables, the inventories of both reactors were held constant (equal to measured values) in all simulations. This inventory distribution is not necessarily optimal, but a high carbonator bed pressure was chosen to ensure process performance is not significantly limited by gas–solids contact time. Reactor inventories were held constant by automatically adjusting two control parameters: the solids recycling split of the calciner (b_{CC}) and the purge flow. The former is used to control the distribution of solids between the two reactors, and the latter to control the total inventory in the system. Please note that this is not merely a simplifying assumption, but is equivalent to physically controlling the amount of solids extracted or recycled to the reactors in order to achieve a specific inventory distribution. If it was not possible to operate the CaL process with these predefined reactor inventories, the corresponding simulation was excluded from further

Table 1

Specifications of the coal used in the study. AR = as received, DAF = dry and ash-free, VM = Volatile matter, FC = fixed carbon.

Ultimate analysis, DAF [kg/kg]					Proximate analysis, AR [kg/kg]				LHV, AR
C	H	N	S	O	Moisture	Ash	VM	FC	[MJ/kg]
0.905	0.048	0.017	0.011	0.019	0.1	0.126	0.229	0.545	27.11

Table 2
Parameters used in the simulations.

Parameter	Carbonator	Calciner
Bed pressure drop [Pa]	8200	800
Fuel duty [MW]	–	1.5–2.1
Bayonet tube area [m ²]	5.75	–
Heat losses through walls [kW]	50	100
Particle density, sorbent/char [kg/m ³]	1800/550	1800/550
Particle diameter, sorbent/char [μm]	140/–	140/300
Exit density coefficient c_{exit}	0.2	0.5
Circulation coefficient c_{circ}	0.5	0.5
Solids recycling ratios b_{CB} and b_{CC}	0–0.4	0–0.6
Calcination coefficient c_{calc}	–	0.25
Sorbent CO ₂ -carrying coefficient $c_{X,max}$	0.8	–

Table 3
Material inlet conditions.

Parameter	Carbonator	Calciner
Fluidizing gas flow [kg/s]	0.37	0.42–0.64
Fluidizing gas composition [m-%]		
O ₂	5.6	33.8
N ₂	70.5	0
CO ₂	20.8	66.2
H ₂ O	3.0	0
SO ₂	0.15	0
Loop seal air flow [kg/s]	0.09	0.09
Make-up flow [kg/s]	–	0.082
Make-up composition [m-%]		
CaCO ₃	–	98.6
Ash	–	1.4

analysis. The only exception to this rule was a set of five points simulated in a fully coupled mode, i.e., without solids recycling in either reactor, for the purpose of comparing these two operating strategies.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Model validation

The model was validated under oxy-combustion conditions and with the solids recycling valves completely closed ($b_{CC} = b_{CB} = 0$). Fluidizing conditions were typical, with a superficial gas velocity of approximately 3.5 m/s in the carbonator and 4.5 m/s in the calciner. Simulated and measured temperature and pressure profiles of both reactors are shown in Fig. 3. The lower part of the carbonator is operated at a relatively high temperature of 720 °C, but the cooling surfaces in the freeboard reduce the temperature in the upper region close to 650 °C. The bed pressure is relatively high, close to 8 kPa, ensuring long residence times for the calcium particles and good gas–solid contact in the reactor. The calciner is operated with a leaner bed (800 Pa) and at a temperature of approximately 900 °C, which is sufficient to partly calcine the sorbent and sustain a carbon capture efficiency of 80 % in the carbonator. Simulated and measured gas and solids compositions are presented in Fig. 4. Here, too, the agreement is generally reasonable. A slightly higher water vapor content was measured in the carbonator than obtained through a mass balance, but this is likely due to measurement errors and is virtually meaningless from a process performance perspective. The content of ashes (SiO₂) and CaSO₄ also differs slightly from measurements, but again, the effect on the overall calcium looping process is minimal. The deviations in CaCO₃ content are worth noting, as they are an alternative way of defining the carbon capture efficiency compared to that indicated by gas composition measurements. However, as shown in Table 4, the carbon balance is not entirely closed, suggesting small inaccuracies in the measurements. Since gas measurements are considered relatively accurate, it would be reasonable to presume that the solids composition measured by periodic sampling is more of an estimate rather than a precise reading. Bearing this in mind, the model results appear to be well in line with measurements.

Fig. 3. Simulated (lines) and measured (Arias et al., 2018) (markers) temperature and pressure profiles.

Fig. 4. Simulated and measured gas and solid compositions at the outlets of the carbonator (CB) and calciner (CC).

Table 4
Measured and simulated carbon balances around the carbonator.

	Carbon balance, kg _C /hr	
	Measured	Simulated
Flue gas in	74.6	74.6
Flue gas out	15.1	14.2
Solids in	52.6	33.0
Solids out	88.1	93.4
Balance	24.0	0.0

3.2. Reactor temperature map

The results obtained by varying fuel input and b_{CB} can be plotted on a map with the temperatures of the calciner and carbonator on the x - and y -axes, respectively, as shown in Fig. 5. The simulation data is available at Secomandi et al. (2025). Exit temperatures were selected to represent the reactor temperatures in these maps, as it is the temperature of the solids transferred from one reactor to the other that determines the sensible heat flows between reactors. The simulated points were connected with Delaunay triangulation, which allows for the interpolation of the results and the generation of a continuous surface that represents the operational window of the system. Points at which the predefined pressures cannot be maintained are shown as blue markers, while the remaining (valid) points are shown in yellow. The surface extends far to the east and south—farther than necessary for this analysis, considering that the risk of sintering grows at temperatures higher than 950 °C, for example. As such, the maps presented in the following sections have been framed so that excessively high or low temperatures are not shown.

Fig. 6a shows that increasing the fuel load increases the temperature in both reactors, as the transfer of solids between reactors causes the carbonator to heat up when the temperature in the calciner rises. Conversely, increasing b_{CB} causes the temperature of the calciner to increase and that of the carbonator to decrease, as the transfer flow decreases and less sensible heat is transferred between reactors.

The round markers show the region to which the operation of the CaL process is constrained when no solids are recycled in either reactor, with the square marker showing the measured reference point. With all other boundary conditions held constant, fuel input is the only parameter controlling the temperatures of both reactors, and the process can only be operated on a narrow line on the map surface. The inventory distribution also shifts as hydrodynamic conditions change, i.e., as fuel input increases, so does the fluidizing gas flow to the calciner, and more of the total inventory is transferred to the carbonator.

In contrast, when solids recycling is employed, the inventories of both reactors can be held constant over a large portion of the map by adjusting the recycling ratio of the calciner, b_{CC} . This blue area is bounded to the northwest by a curve that consists of two segments. To the northeast of the reference point, i.e., the direction of increasing fuel input, this line follows the $b_{CB} = 0$ line. As fuel input is increased, the rising gas velocity in the calciner increases the solids entrainment rate, and a larger share of the total inventory would be transferred to the carbonator were it not balanced by an increase in b_{CC} . The b_{CC} values needed to maintain constant inventories are shown in Fig. 6b. Conversely, to the southwest of the reference point, a decrease in fuel load causes solids to accumulate in the calciner. In this case, however, this inventory shift cannot be prevented by further decreasing b_{CC} as it is already zero. Since the bed inventories cannot be held at their predefined values, these points are excluded from the map. As b_{CB} is gradually increased, the bed inventories can be held constant with increasingly small fuel inputs. The operating window is thus bounded by the $b_{CB} = 0$ and $b_{CC} = 0$ curves to the north and west, respectively, of the reference point. Note that it may be possible to run the process by recycling solids only in the carbonator or the calciner, but that would result in different solids inventories in the reactors and is not within the scope of this work.

3.3. Process performance

With the operational range of the CaL process well defined, the next step is to determine the most suitable operating point under the given constraints. If only the carbon capture efficiency of the process is considered, the best performance (90%) is achieved at a temperature of approximately 590 °C in the carbonator and 930 °C in the calciner, as shown in Fig. 7a. According to Fig. 6b, this temperature pair occurs when 25% of the solids entrained in the carbonator are recycled, and the fuel input is reduced to approximately 1.75 MW_{LHV}. For comparison, a value of 81% was obtained for the capture rate in the reference case, and Fig. 7a suggests that it would not be possible to reach significantly higher capture rates without restricting the transfer of solids between reactors.

In order to identify the main factors limiting carbon capture, the partial derivatives of the carbonation rate (Eq. (13)) were computed with respect to carbonator temperature, sorbent conversion, and inventory, as described in Appendix B. The derivatives were then combined into a single image by scaling the values of the red, green, and blue channels of each point in the map by the values of the corresponding three partial derivatives. For a more meaningful comparison, the derivatives were scaled following $10\text{ K} = 1\text{ mol.}\%_{\text{CaCO}_3} = 1000\text{ Pa}$. Thus, the resulting image (Fig. 7b) displays the relative importance of each of these three variables in increasing the overall carbonation rate in the reac-

Fig. 5. Grid of points simulated: invalid points are shown in blue; valid points are shown in yellow. The blue surface shows the area to which the results have been interpolated. The different shades of blue are meaningless.

Fig. 6. Solids recycling ratios in the carbonator and calciner (solid lines) and fuel input (dotted lines, MW_{LHV}). The blue surface represents the area accessible by varying the amount of solids recycled to the carbonator, while round markers show the area accessible without employing solids recycling in either reactor. The reference point is marked by a square marker.

(a) Carbon capture efficiency. Round markers show the area accessible without recycling solids, with the reference point marked by a square marker.

(b) Color-coded derivatives of carbonation wrt. temperature (red), sorbent conversion (green), and inventory (blue).

Fig. 7. Maps of carbon capture efficiency and carbonation partial derivatives.

tor by showing regions most sensitive to changes in temperature in red, sorbent conversion in green, and inventory in blue. As can be seen, the top area of the map is primarily limited by equilibrium (temperature), and the bottom region is limited by the availability of active sorbent. There is also a narrow green strip on the left edge of the map, where a low calciner temperature leads to limited calcination in the reactor and an insufficient flow of active sorbent being supplied to the carbonator. The relative effect of sorbent inventory (blue) appears to be small everywhere, suggesting that further increasing the carbonator inventory would not be a particularly effective strategy in improving process performance. All derivatives are relatively small in the dark region in the center of the map, which indicates that performance could not be significantly improved by changing any single variable. Instead, the limitations of both equilibrium and sorbent activity would need to be addressed simultaneously by supplying the carbonator with a greater flow of active sorbent but with a reduced heat input. This cannot be done by varying the transfer rate of solids alone, but could be achieved by installing larger heat exchangers and increasing the make-up flow, for instance. However, both methods lead to increased fuel consumption, and they are not within the scope of this work.

As seen in Fig. 7a, carbon capture efficiency decreases from a maximum of ~90% to 80~85% when the exit temperature of the carbonator increases to about 640 °C \pm 5 °C. Initially, this could seem to contradict expectations as 650 °C is often considered a favorable operating temperature for the carbonator. However, this apparent contradiction is explained by the temperature gradient inside the carbonator, shown for the reference point in Fig. 3a. While the temperature at the reactor outlet is 640 °C, the dense bed operates at a temperature close to 720 °C, and carbonation is inhibited in the lower part of the reactor by equilibrium. This behavior is illustrated in Fig. 8a. Despite carbonation

only being interrupted over a height of two meters, over 80% of the solid mass is situated in the first three meters of the carbonator, and the amount of carbonation taking place in the remaining length of the reactor is limited. As such, the temperature of the dense bed plays a significant role in determining the carbon capture efficiency of the process. For comparison, corresponding profiles for the best-performing case are also shown. As can be seen, the lower temperature allows the reaction to progress further in the dense bed, resulting in clearly improved performance. The robustness of the results near this region can be demonstrated by a simple sensitivity analysis where the overall carbonation rate of the best-performing case is modified by \pm 50%. With the higher reaction rate, carbon capture efficiency increases from 90.3% to 91.3%, while the reduced reaction rate causes it to decrease to 87.8%. This insensitivity is explained by the proximity of the CO₂ concentration to equilibrium in the dense bed, as illustrated in Fig. 8b.

A transition from equilibrium-limited to sorbent-limited operation appears to occur as the carbonator temperature decreases from ~620 °C to ~580 °C. While restricting solids circulation reduces the flow of CaO supplied to the carbonator, the dependence of the maximum CO₂-carrying capacity on the carbonation temperature also plays a significant role in determining the performance of the CaL process. In addition to the activity of all age fractions being reduced as temperature decreases, this reduced activity causes the aging process itself to be accelerated, as particles are carbonated closer to their maximum carrying capacity if the amount of carbonation occurring in the reactor is constant (see Eqs. (21) and (22)). As a result, decreasing the carbonator temperature by throttling the transfer flow of solids comes with a meaningful penalty to the availability of active sorbent. The average CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent, as estimated by the population balance model, is shown in Fig. 8b. The average activity depends on the carbonator

(a) Simulated CO₂ concentration and equilibrium profiles of the reference case and the best-performing case. Cases marked by ($\pm 50\%$) had the carbonation reaction rate increased or decreased by 50%

(b) Estimated CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent at steady state

Fig. 8. CO₂ concentration profiles (a) and estimated CO₂-carrying capacities (b).

temperature and the carbon capture efficiency, with higher activity visible in areas of high temperature or weak carbon capture. It is worth noting that the results presented here are a rough estimate, as despite efforts to consider key variables affecting the CO₂-carrying capacity of the sorbent, the sorbent deactivation process is complex and depends on numerous factors that cannot be reasonably incorporated into a model such as this.

Finally, Fig. 9 shows the carbon capture efficiency achieved by varying solids transfer rates. The figure clearly shows that increasing solids transfer past 1.2~1.4 kg/s negatively influences the maximum achievable capture efficiency. While a sufficient flow of active sorbent is cru-

cial for efficient carbon capture, the sensible heat supplied by the circulating solids sets a limit on the maximum solids circulation rate that can be sustained before performance declines. Therefore, the net effect of reducing solids transfer depends on the extent to which carbonation is limited by equilibrium and sorbent activity. If carbonation is limited primarily by equilibrium, the benefits of lowering the carbonator temperature and consequently the equilibrium CO₂ concentration outweigh the loss in sorbent activity and vice versa. Reducing fuel input to cool the carbonator may lower the calciner temperature excessively, decreasing calcination efficiency and, as a result, negatively impacting carbonation. As such, the transfer rate of solids should only be reduced when the

Fig. 9. Capture efficiency versus solids transfer flow from the calciner, with marker colours representing values of the exit temperatures of the carbonator.

temperature difference between reactors must be increased, i.e., when the performance of the carbonator is limited primarily by equilibrium and the temperature of the calciner cannot be further lowered without a significant penalty to calcination efficiency. This finding is consistent with earlier results by [Ylätaalo et al. \(2013\)](#), who found that the highest carbon capture efficiency would be reached with a molar looping ratio $\dot{n}_{\text{CaO}}/\dot{n}_{\text{CO}_2}$ of approximately 15 before decreasing due to unsuitable reactor temperatures as solids transfer was increased further. This value is close to the ratio of 16 obtained in this study for the best-performing case. In an experimental study where the transfer flow was controlled by a cone valve, [Charitos et al. \(2010b\)](#) also reached a carbon capture efficiency close to the maximum allowed by equilibrium with a looping ratio of approximately 16. It should be noted that studies on the trade-off of sacrificing sorbent activity for more suitable thermal conditions in the reactors are scarce, and that operating conditions generally differ from those studied in this paper. As an example, the study by [Charitos et al. \(2011\)](#) employed a BFB carbonator.

The results of this paper show that a means to control the solids transfer rate is clearly necessary in situations such as this, as significantly higher carbon capture rates may be achieved while simultaneously reducing fuel consumption. The recycling of solids may also be used to control the distribution of solids between reactors and ensure a dense bed forms in the carbonator, but that is outside the scope of this work.

4. Conclusions

The effect of controlling the transfer flow of solids on reactor temperatures and the overall performance of the CaL process was analyzed using a dual-reactor model. As illustrated by the temperature maps, the CaL process becomes far more flexible to operate if the transfer flow of solids can be reliably controlled. Additionally, the operating window of the process may be situated in a suboptimal region of the operation map if the transfer flows are determined purely by hydrodynamics, as high solids transfer rates decrease the temperature difference between the two reactors and may result in either excessive carbonator temperatures or insufficient calciner temperatures for efficient operation. As such, the solids transfer rate must be controllable to a high degree of accuracy and flexibility to respond to potential fluctuations in fluidization velocity or during load changes. These results highlight the importance of developing and adopting methods to reliably control the solid flows between dual fluidized bed reactors.

The presented modeling method and tool allow for examining the process under different conditions and identifying favorable operating conditions. For example, the simulations performed suggest that the carbon capture efficiency of the measured operation point could be increased by about 9% units to an efficiency of 90% by restricting the flow of solids transferred between reactors. Understanding such operating points is a critical step in the design of CaL systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Markus Secomandi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis; **Eemeli Anetjärvi:** Writing – original draft, Software, Investigation; **Markku Nikku:** Writing – review & editing; **Kari Myöhänen:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration; **Jouni Ritvanen:** Supervision, Software, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Data has been made available on Zenodo and a separate Data in Brief article will be submitted.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Population balance model

In this section, we derive the equations used to build the population balance model that was used to estimate the average CO₂-carrying capacity of a sorbent. This model was devised to converge to a steady-state solution with a reactor model, using results from the reactor model as input. Since we are concerned only with steady-state results, we make simplifications such as assuming that the age distribution in the carbonator is equal to that of the calciner and assuming that the total rate of calcination in the calciner corresponds to the difference in the carbonate content of sorbent entering and exiting the calciner. The first assumption allows us to reduce the number of population balances needed in the CaL system from two to one. The second improves the robustness of the model to sudden changes in calcination rate. It drastically simplifies the model by allowing us to assume that calcination, and thus sorbent aging, occurs as the carbonated solids enter the calciner.

Before deriving the equations used in the population balance model, we make a few definitions to simplify the process further. Since X_{max} is defined as the share of carbonate in all Ca-based species, the ash fraction of solids is not needed. Therefore, variables such as the total sorbent inventory (n), the molar flow of carbonated sorbent entering the calciner (\dot{n}_m), and the molar flow of make-up (\dot{n}_0) refer specifically to the flow of ash-free solids. Similarly, the carbonate content (X) refers to the molar share of CaCO₃ in ash-free solids.

Since the age fraction r_N is the ratio of particles of age N to the total number of particles, its derivative is given by

$$\frac{dr_N}{dt} = \frac{d(n_N/n)}{dt} = \frac{\frac{dn_N}{dt} - r_N \frac{dn}{dt}}{n} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The rate of change of the total inventory is due to the make-up and purge flows, i.e.:

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = \dot{n}_0 - \dot{n}_p, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

whereas the rate of change of age fraction N is also affected by the aging of age fractions N and $N - 1$:

$$\frac{dn_N}{dt} = \dot{n}_0 r_{0,N} - \dot{n}_p r_N + \dot{n}_{\text{aging},N-1} - \dot{n}_{\text{aging},N}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Here, $r_{0,N}$ are the age fractions of the make-up, which are one for $N = 0$ and zero for the remaining age fractions. Combining these two equations with Eq. (A.1) yields:

$$\frac{dr_N}{dt} = \frac{(\dot{n}_0 r_{0,N} + \dot{n}_{\text{aging},N-1} - \dot{n}_{\text{aging},N}) - r_N \dot{n}_0}{n} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The aging process is related to the changing relative conversion of the sorbent ($X^* = X/X_{\text{max}}$) as follows:

$$\dot{n}_{\text{aging},N} = \dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_N (X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^*). \quad (\text{A.5})$$

That is, if the sorbent is carbonated to its saturation limit ($X_{CB}^* = 1$) and then entirely calcined ($X_{CC}^* = 0$), its age increases by one. If carbonation or calcination is incomplete, only a fraction of the sorbent is

moved to the next age bracket. A key question in a model such as this is how carbonation and calcination are distributed among the different age fractions. Here, we assume that all age fractions older than $N = 0$ are carbonated to the same relative conversion, i.e.,

$$X^* = \frac{X_1}{X_{\max,1}} = \frac{X_2}{X_{\max,2}} = \dots = \frac{X_N}{X_{\max,N}}, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

whereas uncalcined limestone ($N = 0$) is assumed to consist purely of CaCO_3 , and its relative conversion is always one. Similarly, we assume that all CaCO_3 entering the calciner is calcined to the same extent, i.e.:

$$E_{\text{calc}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc}}}{\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{\text{in}} X_{CB}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc},0}}{\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_0} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc},1}}{\dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_1 X_{CB,1}} = \dots = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc},N}}{\dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_N X_{CB,N}}, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where E_{calc} is the calcination efficiency, \dot{n}_{calc} is the total calcination rate (in mol/s), and $\dot{n}_{\text{calc},N}$ is the calcination rate of age fraction N . The relationship between the calcination rate and the change in relative conversion in the calciner ($X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^*$) may be obtained from Eq. (A.7). The carbonate content of the circulating solids, X_{CB} , can be split into two parts, namely uncalcined limestone ($r_0 X_0 = r_0$) and all other fractions ($\sum_{N=1}^{\infty} r_N X_{CB,N}$). Solving for \dot{n}_{calc} and applying Eq. (A.6) we obtain:

$$\dot{n}_{\text{calc}} = E_{\text{calc}} \left(\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \left(r_0 + X_{CB}^* \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} r_N X_{\max,N} \right) \right). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Solving for $E_{\text{calc}} X_{CB}^*$ and substituting $E_{\text{calc}} X_{CB}^* = X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^*$ yields the desired expression:

$$X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^* = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc}} - E_{\text{calc}}(\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_0)}{\dot{n}_{\text{in}} \sum_{N=1}^{\infty} r_N X_{\max,N}} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{calc}} - E_{\text{calc}}(\dot{n}_0 + \dot{n}_{\text{in}} r_0)}{\dot{n}_{\text{in}} X_{\max}}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

The final expression for dr_N/dt is:

$$\frac{dr_N}{dt} = \frac{\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(r_{N-1} - r_N)(X_{CB}^* - X_{CC}^*) + \dot{n}_0(r_{0,N} - r_N)}{n}. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

These two equations allow using results from the reactor model, such as the total sorbent inventory and solid flows and compositions, to solve the steady-state populations of all age fractions.

Appendix B. Partial derivatives of carbonation reaction rate

Simplified derivatives of the carbonation rate equation were calculated in order to identify the most significant limiting factors for the simulated operating points. The expression for carbonation rate (Eq. (13)) was rewritten as the product of a constant and three functions of T , X_{act} , and p . For this section, we define X_{act} as the active fraction of calcium, i.e., $X_{\text{act}} = X_{\max} - X_{\text{CaCO}_3}$. The carbonation rate in element i is given by:

$$r_i(T_i, X_{\text{act},i}, p) = c f(T_i) g(X_{\text{act},i}) h_i(p), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where

$$c = 0.3429 X_{\text{CaO},i}^{0.1} M_{\text{CaO}}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

$$f(T_i) = \exp\left(\frac{-2309}{T_i}\right) (C_{\text{CO}_2,i} - C_{\text{eq}}(T_i)), \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$g(X_{\text{act},i}) = (X_{\text{act},i})^{2/3}, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$h_i(p) = n_{\text{Ca},i}. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The term $X_{\text{CaO}}^{0.1}$ can be neglected in most situations, as most of the calcium present is typically in the form of CaO. For the sake of simplicity, the CO_2 concentration of all 1D elements was assumed to be constant (unaffected by changes in T , X_{act} , or p). The expression for C_{eq} was given in Eq. (14). The function $g(X_{\text{act}})$ accounts for changes in both carbonate content X_{CaCO_3} and CO_2 -carrying capacity X_{\max} , since the effect of

decreasing X_{CaCO_3} on carbonation rate is exactly the same as that of increasing X_{\max} . The total calcium inventory $n_{\text{Ca,tot}}$ and the total pressure loss over the reactor Δp are related by:

$$\Delta p = \frac{g m_{\text{tot}}}{A_c} = \frac{g}{A_c} \frac{\bar{M}_{\text{Ca}}}{1 - W_{\text{ash}}} n_{\text{Ca,tot}}, \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration constant, m_{tot} is the total mass of solids in the reactor, A_c is the cross-sectional area of the reactor, \bar{M}_{Ca} is the average molar weight of Ca-compounds, and W_{ash} is the mass fraction of ash (inerts) in the solids. By assuming that the distribution of solids within the reactor (i.e., the ratios $n_{\text{Ca},i}/n_{\text{Ca,tot}}$) is not significantly affected by small changes in inventory, a simplified relation between the local calcium inventory and the overall pressure loss across the reactor is obtained:

$$n_{\text{Ca},i} = \frac{n_{\text{Ca},i}}{n_{\text{Ca,tot}}} n_{\text{Ca,tot}} = \frac{n_{\text{Ca},i}}{n_{\text{Ca,tot}}} \frac{A_c (1 - W_{\text{ash},i})}{g \bar{M}_{\text{Ca},i}} \Delta p. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Thus, the partial derivative of the carbonation rate with respect to temperature for element i is:

$$\frac{\partial r_i}{\partial T_i} = c g(X_{\text{act},i}) h_i(p) \exp\left(\frac{-2309}{T_i}\right) \left[\frac{2309}{T_i^2} (C_{\text{CO}_2,i} - C_{\text{eq},i}) - \frac{dC_{\text{eq}}}{dT_i} \right], \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where

$$\frac{dC_{\text{eq}}}{dT_i} = \frac{4.137 \times 10^{12}}{RT_i^3} \exp\left(\frac{-20474}{T_i}\right) (20474 - T_i). \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Correspondingly, the partial derivative of the carbonation rate with respect to sorbent conversion is:

$$\frac{\partial r_i}{\partial X_i} = -0.67 c f(T_i) h_i(p) (X_{\text{act}})^{-0.33}, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

and the partial with respect to pressure loss over the reactor is:

$$\frac{\partial r_i}{\partial p} = c f(T_i) g(X_{\text{act},i}) \frac{n_{\text{Ca},i}}{n_{\text{Ca,tot}}} \frac{A_c (1 - W_{\text{ash},i})}{g \bar{M}_{\text{Ca},i}}. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

The derivatives for carbonation over the entire reactor are calculated as the sum of the contributions of all elements, e.g.:

$$\frac{\partial r}{\partial T} = \sum_i \frac{\partial r_i}{\partial T_i}. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

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